

Women Students Perception towards Entrepreneurship

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Introduction

The term entrepreneur originated from a French word ‘entreprendre’ which means to undertake, in early 19th century it denoted a person who runs a musical institution. Thus it refers to any individual, who sets up business enterprise, taking financial risks to earn profits; they are genuinely motivated by various factors around them, respond to it and act to change by inventing or by reinventing a product or services in the society.

Entrepreneurship refers ‘the capacity and willingness to develop organize and manage a business venture along with any of its risks in order to make a profit, they innovate and create something difficult with value by, devoting time and effort and assuming the financial, psychological, and social risks in an action orientated perspective and receives the resulting awards of monetary and personal satisfaction. Some authors describes them as an instrument of change, agent who introduces various types of innovations; new products, new ways of manufacturing, or any novelty introduced into the system, hence an entrepreneur is the agent who ‘upsets’ the ‘existing equilibrium’, and innovative risk taking is an essential component of the make-up of an entrepreneur.

Importance of Entrepreneurs in Indian Economy

Entrepreneurship has been considered as one of the most significant factors in the development of a country and they are often seen as humans with super abilities; they are ambitious and work hard with persistence. They strike out on their own to improve this society, and they constantly take actions to pursue their goals.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the Women Students perception towards entrepreneurship.
- To examine the factors that influence students in entrepreneurship.
- To study the level of awareness among the students regarding schemes provided to entrepreneurs.

Review of Literature

Entrepreneurship Education enables the student with the knowledge, skills and provides motivation to encourage entrepreneurial studies in a variety of setting. Such type of education designed to change the attitude of the students, and it's the process which equips them with the skills and knowledge to enable them to start and manage a business enterprise. Thus, an entrepreneurship education is not just about teaching someone to run a business, it is also about encouraging creative thinking and promoting a strong sense of self-worth and empowerment.

Mr. Abdul Jaleel (2017) a study found that the youth must be encouraged to start their own businesses and be taught that making mistakes is one way of learning. Therefore, a financial support system which allows for trial and error should be developed for entrepreneurs starting their first business.

Dr. Manisha (2016) a study concludes that there are various types of barriers are faced while selecting entrepreneur as a career and she also recommends to develop the strategies for campus entrepreneurship and overall youth entrepreneurship development in Sonipat district.

Zuzana Papulová (2015) in the study "entrepreneurship in the eyes of the young generation" reveals that entrepreneurship is perceived positively, as a way to increase employment and to have a better future, it is necessary to use all skills and abilities and create good conditions especially for young generation to be able them to prepare themselves for the future.

University of Calabar, Cross River State (2014-2015) studied on Attitude of students towards entrepreneurship studies in Nigeria; surveyed a random sample of 225 respondents out of 20,193 undergraduate students and concluded that students attitude towards entrepreneurial studies are positive and recommend institutions to adopt, entrepreneurial learning and to allow students to mix during such activities to recourse their level of creativity.

Analysis and Interpretations**Table Showing the Opinion on Young Students Starting a Business**

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	79	79
No	21	21
Total	100	100

Interpretation

This table shows, that majority (79%) of the students think that young adults can start a business, and 21% of the students don't agree with it.

Table Showing the Interest in Starting a Business Venture

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	69	69
No	31	31
Total	100	100

Interpretation

The above table represents, that out of 100 students 69% of them are interested to start a business and 31% of them are not interested.

Table Showing the Factors that Influence the Entrepreneurship

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Innovation	16	16
Monetary rewards	28	28
Employment opportunities	29	29
Social status	27	27
Total	100	100

Interpretation

The above shows the students inspirations to start a business. 29% of them start a business to provide employment opportunities, 28% of them start to earn more income, and 27% of the students choose it to increase their social status and 16% of them choose it, to provide a product or a service.

Table Showing the Awareness on Entrepreneurial Schemes

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	28	28
No	72	72
Total	100	100

Interpretation

This table shows that majority of the respondents are unaware of the schemes provided to entrepreneurs and only 28% of the students are aware of the schemes.

Table Shows Whether Academic Institutions Should Encourage Students in Entrepreneurship

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	98	98
No	2	2
Total	100	100

Interpretation

The above table shows that 98% of the respondents that the academic institutions to encourage students in entrepreneurship and only 2% of them disagree.

Garrett Ranking Method

The Limitations for Choosing Entrepreneur as a Career

Particulars						Mean Score	Garett Table Value	Garett Rank
Fear of failure	12	18	27	32	11	87.42	95	4
Lack of confidence	34	17	38	9	12	89.57	90	2
Lack of family support	12	18	20	8	42	86.60 87	5	
Lack of business experience	43	26	12	14	5	90.74	85	1
Difficult in accessing funds	31	9	23	24	13	88.75	83	3

Interpretation

The table shows that Lack Business Experience secures the First Rank with the Mean Score 90.74. Hence, it is concluded that Educational Institutions shall encourage the students to participate in ED Bazaar and related competitions where they may get some business experience

Findings

1. It is found that majority (79%) of the students agrees that, young adults can start a business and 21% of the students are not interested to start a business.
2. It is found that majority of the respondents (71%) of the respondents do not have entrepreneur as friend or as a family.
3. It is found that lack of business experience and confidence, and fear of failure are the major obstacles in choosing entrepreneurship as a career.
4. The major reasons for students in this era, in choosing entrepreneur as career are to generate employment opportunities as well as to earn money.
5. It is found that only 16% of the students are inspired to produce a product or to provide a service in the economy.
6. The study revealed that, all the (100%) respondents agree that, entrepreneurship is an honorable profession.
7. Majority (98%) of the respondents think that the academic institutions should encourage the students to consider entrepreneurship.
8. Majority (81%) of the respondents agrees that, self-employment/entrepreneurship must be considered more important than any other subject.
9. The study shows that, majority (72%) of the students are unaware of the schemes provided by the government to entrepreneurs.
10. The study shows that, 85% of the students feel that the laws should be business friendly.

Suggestions

1. The academic institutions should foster entrepreneurial initiative among their students by providing workshops, education which can encourage and enhance their abilities.
2. The schemes provided by the Indian government to entrepreneurs and such entrepreneurial activities can be published in any of the media, to initiate the young adults, as they are unaware of such schemes.
3. The students have to develop more knowledge in business planning, business laws, as well as the application of accounting programs in their start ups to be successful in any field.
4. The academic institutions should evaluate the business opportunities, and help their students to generate business idea, as well as the practical knowledge about the process of starting a business.
5. The students should perceive their interest and focus on their abilities irrespective of their identity to choose a field of their interest and have courage to do it in the reality.

Conclusion

This study was focused on identifying the students perception towards entrepreneurship, the research results showed that despite majority of the students think to start a business, most of them do not want to follow their interest in entrepreneurship. Lack of business experience and confidence and lack of family support as well as the fear of failure hinders students to initiate entrepreneurial activities, as entrepreneurs are changing agents in the society; they develop the economy as whole in various ways.

As many youngsters are inspired by various reasons to start a business, they lack the technical and professional knowledge to start one and majority of them are unaware of the governmental schemes provided to entrepreneurial activities, thus many of their ideas are not executed due to hesitations and doubts. Hence the interested individuals should be given proper guidance and trainings to develop his/her own business ideas with an assurance to succeed.

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